

Deliverable D1.12

Work Package 1

Responsible Partner: UoS

Contributing partners:

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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Leader	University of Surrey		
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	<p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p><u>Other recipient(s):</u></p>
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Overview: One Health EJP Newsletters

The One Health EJP produces two different newsletters throughout the year, the quarterly Consortium Newsletter and the bi-annual External Newsletter. These newsletters are created and disseminated by the Communications Team at the University of Surrey. The content of the newsletters is determined by the Communications Team with input from consortium members and the Project Management Team (PMT). In the third year, the newsletters were sent using MailChimp which allowed audiences to be monitored and updated when necessary, in accordance with the changes made to the consortium members spreadsheet (for the Consortium and External newsletters) or online subscriptions via the form on the One Health EJP website (for the External Newsletter), and complies with GDPR. The internal mailing list had 800 subscribers at the end of the third year with between 21-27% of these subscribers opening the Consortium Newsletter when it is issued. The External newsletter had 607 subscribers with between 30-50% of subscribers opening the External Newsletter when it is issued. Additionally, MailChimp allows the Communications Team to monitor the links clicked in each newsletter and the number of people unsubscribing from the newsletter, these metrics inform the One Health EJP's Communication Strategy which is constantly evolving. MailChimp also integrates with Google Analytics and can track the traffic to the One Health EJP website from the newsletters.

The content and design of each newsletter is validated by the PMT before being sent. When the newsletters have been sent, they are also published on the One Health EJP website (<https://onehealthjep.eu/newsletters/>) and shared on Twitter and LinkedIn.

Consortium Newsletters

In 2020, the Consortium Newsletters were sent in February, June and November. These newsletters target all One Health EJP consortium members and were disseminated to PMT, Institute Representative, Scientific Representatives, Programme Owner Representative, Programme Managers Committee members, Project Leaders, Project mailing lists, PhD students and supervisors, CCPs and stakeholders. Members were encouraged to disseminate the newsletters within their institutes. Although these newsletters were specifically targeted towards consortium members, they did not contain any confidential information and therefore could be widely disseminated. For example, they were shared on the One Health EJP social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn) and also posted on the Newsletters page of the One Health EJP website.

The Consortium Newsletters followed a similar format and generally included the following sections:

- Highlights
- Events
- Key Announcements
- Updates from Work Packages
- Updates from JRP, JIP and PhD projects
- Publications (where appropriate)
- Social media links
- News from One Health EJP stakeholders

This format was subject to change depending on the content available.

February 2020: <https://mailchi.mp/6e44f81793d9/one-health-ejp-february-consortium-newsletter>

The highlights section of this newsletter highlighted:

- The start of the second round of JRPs and JIPs.
- The One Health EJP internal events survey and the importance of completing this for dissemination purposes.
- That application for the 2020 ASM Satellite Workshop was open.
- The publication of the One Health EJP Dissemination Procedure and Publication Policy and links to these documents.

The events section featured:

- The first One Health EJP CPD module.
- The Scientific Steering Board Meeting, Lisbon.
- The One Health EJP Satellite Workshop Meeting, Prague
- The One Health EJP ASM 2020, Prague.

The key announcement highlighted that the second One Health EJP ASM would be held in Prague at the end of May 2020. This newsletter also highlighted the start of more One Health EJP projects, including JRPs, JIPs and PhDs. Images from four project kick-off meetings were a powerful tool to demonstrate the collaboration throughout the One Health EJP. A new version of the One Health EJP deliverable template was also announced for all consortium members. A new section was added to this newsletter to introduce new members of the One Health EJP. The “Getting to Know You” section welcomed new members to the Communications Team and WP3 Team. Updates from the Work Package 5 and 6 were also published in February’s newsletter, which included updating the consortium of the ongoing science to policy translation and funding opportunities for the Education and Training activities. Other sections featured an update if members were looking to publish food safety research, information about an upcoming bioinformatic webinar and how the Communication Team could offer support for hosting events.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (the number of recipient who opened the campaign):	150/530 (28.3%)
Total number of opens (the total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. This counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient)	494
Number of links clicked	42

June 2020: <https://mailchi.mp/2288c975bcad/one-health-ejp-consortium-newsletter-june-2020>

The highlights section of this newsletter highlighted:

- The hosting of the first virtual One Health EJP ASM.
- The publication of the 2019 One Health EJP Annual Report.
- The One Health EJP internal events survey and the importance of completing this for dissemination purposes.
- The One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI).
- New One Health EJP stakeholders.

The events section featured:

- World Zoonoses Day.
- The One Health EJP Summer School.
- The Stakeholder Committee Meeting.
- Programme Owners/Programme Managers joint meeting.

The key announcement focussed on the One Health EJP ASM 2020 which was converted from a physical event to a virtual one. It highlighted the global audience that the event attracted in addition to the first One Health EJP PhD Three-Minute Thesis (3MT) competition and prize winners. The promotional video that was created by an external company to highlight the success of the event also featured at the end of the key announcement section. The next section of the newsletter highlighted the success of the Work Package 5 team in extending the One Health EJP Stakeholder Committee to include EEA, EMA, FAO and WHO-Europe. The One Health EJP Outcome Inventory was also reported on for the first time since being created by Work Package 5. This newsletter also reported on the One Health EJP's response to the COVID-19 pandemic. This included informing consortium members of the new "Latest News" page on the website which was created initially to report on COVID-19, making members aware of links between COVID-19 related need of stakeholders and One Health EJP activities in a new document and also highlighting how the PhD students continued with their research despite the pandemic. The final sections of this newsletter highlighted an update from the AIR SAMPLE project and reported on the Short Term Missions that took place before the pandemic.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (the number of recipient who opened the campaign):	156/742 (21%)
Total number of opens (the total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. This counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient)	702
Number of links clicked	42

November 2020: <https://mailchi.mp/d48b7048c8ce/one-health-ejp-consortium-newsletter-november-2020>

The highlights section of this newsletter highlighted:

- The save the date for the One Health EJP ASM 2021.
- The publication of the Dissemination Information Pack to support all consortium members with disseminating their outcomes.
- The One Health EJP internal events survey and the importance of completing this for dissemination purposes.
- The Stakeholders Committee Meeting
- The Joint Programme Owners/Programme Managers meeting.

The events section featured:

- COHESIVE annual meeting
- 6th Cogwheel workshop

The key announcement focussed on the One Health EJP's attendance at the World One Health Congress. It highlighted key speakers and posters from the One Health EJP activities, and the potential impact the consortium's research can have. The congress ended on One Health Day

which is a social media campaign that the Communications Team take part in each year, and this was also highlighted in the November edition of the newsletter. The confirmation of new One Health EJP stakeholders was also reported following October's stakeholder committee meeting and stakeholder testimonials were a key feature in this section of the newsletter. This newsletter took the opportunity to reflect on the successes of the virtual Education and Training activities that took place in 2020. The Summer School and Communication and Media Workshop were highlights of 2020 and were highlighted with image montages and testimonials from the events. Upcoming Education and Training activities such as the CPD module and Summer School in 2021 were also advertised with save the date flyers. The final article in this newsletter was a highlight of EU-JAMRAI's antimicrobial resistance competition, a competition that the One Health EJP was involved in judging and promoting.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

Number of opens (the number of recipient who opened the campaign):	162/761 (21.2%)
Total number of opens (the total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients. This counts includes multiple opens from individual recipient)	542
Number of links clicked	21

Overall Consortium Newsletter Statistics:

Overall, the number of consortium members opening the newsletter is between 21-28%, which was similar to that of year 2. According to MailChimp the average number of opens for a newsletter should be between 15-25%, therefore these newsletters are performing as expected. The Communications Team would like to improve these statistics because the newsletters often contain important information for members. However, important information is also communicated in other ways to ensure it reaches the target audience. November's newsletter has the lowest numbers of interactions, which may be attributed to an information overload on virtual platforms as a result of remote working in 2020. Statistics collected throughout the year for newsletters and events are monitored and email is still the most effect means of communication for consortium members, however the interest in newsletters is less than expected. The Communication Team will investigate ways to improve this for year 4.

External Newsletters:

In 2020, one External Newsletter was published in August. The December edition will now be published in January 2021 as the Communications Team are investigating ways to make this newsletter more appealing to an even larger, global audience. This will be especially important in year 4 when the One Health EJP has more scientific outcomes to disseminate. Currently, the External Newsletter audience includes:

- The general public.
- Scientists external to the One Health EJP.
- Stakeholders.
- Individuals that have subscribed to the One Health EJP mailing list via the website.
 - Anyone that visits the website can join this mailing list.

Currently there are 607 subscribers to the newsletter (as of 21.01.20).

This newsletter is also disseminated to the One Health EJP internal mailing list.

The design and content of the External Newsletter is carefully considered to ensure that it is suitable, and attractive to a wide audience. The language is simpler to that of the Consortium Newsletter and does not contain complex science. There are links to relevant web pages if people wish to read and engage more.

August 2020: <https://mailchi.mp/378db32494ea/one-health-ejp-external-newsletter-aug-2020>

The key highlight of this newsletter was the ASM 2020. The keynote speakers from across the EU and our stakeholder committee, the 3MT competition and the promotional video were all important components of the ASM 2020 that were important to show to an external audience. This newsletter also featured the Annual Report from 2019, a document designed for an external audience to update on the 2019's scientific success. The efforts of Work Package 5's translation of science to policy were highlighted in several ways, including the news of the One Health EJP's new global stakeholders, the stakeholders' committee meeting in May and the One Health EJP Outcome Inventory.

Key events published in this newsletter:

- One Health EJP Summer School.
- The Stakeholder Committee meeting in October.
- Programme Owners/Programme Managers joint meeting.
- The World One Health Congress.

This newsletter also highlighted the start of more One Health EJP projects, including JRPs, JIP and PhDs. Images from four project kick-off meetings demonstrated the collaboration throughout the One Health EJP consortium. Similar to the internal newsletter in June 2020, this newsletter reported on the One Health EJP's response to the COVID-19 pandemic. This included informing subscribers of the new "Latest News" page on the website, making members aware of the "Links between COVID-19 related needs of stakeholders and One Health EJP activities" document and also highlighting how the PhD students maintained their research despite the pandemic. The final sections of this newsletter highlighted an update from the AIR SAMPLE project and reported on the Short Term Missions that took place before the pandemic.

The MailChimp statistics for this newsletter were as follows:

External Mailing List	Internal Mailing List
Number of opens: 173/ 522 (31%)	Number of opens: 170/ 770 (22%)
Total opens: 436	Total opens: 405
Number of links clicked: 81	Number of links clicked: 52

Overall External Newsletter Statistics:

Overall, the external audience engage more with the content of the External Newsletter compared to the internal audience. This may be because the external audience have actively subscribed to the newsletter, whereas the internal audience receive the newsletters by default because they are members of the One Health EJP consortium. This was also a pattern observed in year 2. It is therefore important to maintain the engagement with external audiences, which is why the Communications Team propose to improve the style of the External Newsletter. This may also contribute to increased interest from internal audiences. A

key objective as a result of improving the External Newsletter is to improve sustainability of the One Health EJP and create a legacy for the project.

The number of subscribers to the external mailing list has nearly doubled in the last 12 months, indicating increased interest in the One Health EJP activities. Year 3's external newsletters will focus on more scientific outcomes from the One Health EJP research which may also increase engagement from the internal audiences.

Special Edition COVID-19 Newsletter:

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the One Health EJP issued a newsletter on 23rd March 2020 to inform internal and external audiences of the One Health EJP's response to the pandemic. This newsletter reported on the seven steps that the consortium partners were taking in light of the current situations and a reminder that the One Health EJP has a key focus on outbreak preparedness. The newsletter also informed the audience of the new "Latest News" page on the website which contained detailed and up to date information on the One Health EJP's efforts during the pandemic and related One Health responses. Finally, it was announced that the 2020 ASM would not be a face to face event and that virtual options were being explored.

The MailChimp statistics for COVID-19 newsletter were as follows:

External Mailing List	Internal Mailing List
Number of opens: 216/ 419 (51.5%)	Number of opens: 149/ 541 (27.5%)
Total opens: 512	Total opens: 812
Number of links clicked: 64	Number of links clicked: 55

This newsletter gained significant interest from both mailing lists (more than scheduled Consortium and External newsletters). This is most likely due to how topical the news was in March, at the time of sending this newsletter. It is therefore important to consider this in future news updates.

Future Newsletters:

Future Consortium Newsletters will be disseminated in February, May, August and November 2021.

Future External Newsletters will be disseminated in January, June and December 2021 with a new format.